

IMPROVING THE FACILITATORY COMPETENCES OF FUTURE EDUCATION TEACHERS IN THE CREDIT MODULE SYSTEM

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Abstract. *In the context of the transition of the higher education system to credit-module teaching technologies, the organization of independent learning of students and their orientation to the active learning process is of urgent importance. The purpose of this article is to scientifically and theoretically substantiate the specific pedagogical and psychological characteristics of improving the facilitator competencies of future teachers of the subject "Education" in the credit-module system and to develop practical recommendations. In the research process, scientific literature analysis, pedagogical observation, comparative analysis, as well as psychological diagnostic methods for studying the socio-emotional intelligence of a person were used. Based on the results obtained, the elements of important psychological characteristics (empathy, emotional stability, reflexivity) and pedagogical skills (ability to hear the student, encouraging independent thinking, providing motivation) characteristic of a facilitator-teacher were systematized.*

Keywords: *credit-module system, future teacher, Education, facilitator competence, pedagogical impact, psychological characteristics, empathy, independent learning, emotional intelligence.*

INTRODUCTION

In his Address to the Oliy Majlis, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, emphasized that “we have no right to forget what a unique wealth intellectual and cultural potential is, and that it is crucial to educate and bring to perfection those with rare talents.” Education is not just about teaching certain rules, but also about forming a person’s inner world, attitude to values, and raising him to be a person loyal to the Motherland and useful to the community. Therefore, educators, especially specialists in primary education, must have a deep knowledge of the discipline of education and be able to effectively apply it in their activities. On August 23, 2019, the Ministry of Public Education, chaired by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, Shavkat Mirziyoyev, adopted a resolution on the development of the public education system,[1] increasing the qualifications and authority of educators in society, and raising the spirituality of the younger generation. In order to ensure the implementation of the instructions given at the video selector meeting dedicated to the subject of “Education” in general secondary educational institutions, a draft resolution of the Cabinet of Ministers “On measures for the gradual introduction of the subject of “Education” in general secondary educational institutions” was developed. On July 6, 2020, Resolution No. 422 was adopted[2]. In accordance with the resolution, the subject of “Education” will be taught in general secondary educational institutions by combining the subjects of “Etiquette”, “Sense of Homeland”, “The Idea of National Independence and Fundamentals of Spirituality” and “History of World Religions” in grades 1–9 from the 2020-2021 academic year, and in grades 10–11 from the 2021-2022 academic year. will be gradually introduced into practice within the framework of the general hours allocated to subjects starting

from the academic year.[3] The resolution approved the concept of the subject “Education” for students of general secondary educational institutions. Based on the resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PQ-4884 dated November 6, 2020, a comprehensive program of measures was developed to further improve the fields of education and science. This program sets the task of periodically republishing the “Education” textbook for grades 1-9, using the works of our great grandfathers.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODS

In order to "preserve" the uniqueness of the educational process, the co-authors of the monograph "Education, upbringing, upbringing!" V.A. Karakovsky, Novikova, Selivanova, etc. use another concept of it, proposed by the famous Estonian pedagogue and psychologist O. Yo. Laimce. If we look at the educational process "according to Laimete", then the educational system will not consist of didactics, but on the one hand, it will consist of a psychological-pedagogical system, and on the other - a socio-pedagogical system. In turn, the educational system affects students not only didactically (through teachers, lessons, textbooks, homework), but also as a social factor, through the involvement of children in the environment; it affects through the relationships that arise between parents, teachers and children, through the psychological environment that is formed at the heart of each educational process. In the conditions of the credit-module system, the process of training future teachers of education requires not only the acquisition of professional knowledge and skills, but also the formation of competencies that ensure their personal development and reflexive activity. In particular, in the modern educational paradigm, the teacher is not a provider of knowledge, but also a facilitator of the educational process. The role of the facilitator, who creates a guiding, collaborative environment, is gaining priority. From this point of view, the credit-module system embodies favorable pedagogical and psychological conditions for the development of facilitator competencies in future teachers of education. In this process, the development of the student's subjective activity, the ability to make independent decisions, emotional-intellectual maturity and reflexive thinking is of great importance, which constitute the psychological foundations of facilitator competencies. In modern educational concepts, the professional activity of a teacher of education is interpreted as a person-oriented, socio-cultural and psychologically complex process.

In the context of the integration of education and upbringing, this activity implies a systematic pedagogical impact aimed at the formation of moral values, social behavior and civic consciousness of students. In this regard, the teacher of education appears as a subject that manages personal development and pedagogically supports the process of socialization. The psychological content of professional activity is that the teacher of education carries out educational impact, taking into account the internal needs, emotional state and social experience of the student. As L.S. Vygotsky noted, personal development is formed in the process of social communication, and the teacher is an important factor consciously organizing this process. Therefore, the professional activity of the teacher of education is inextricably linked with pedagogical technologies based on communication, cooperation and reflection.

The requirements for a future teacher of education are complex in pedagogical theory, they are manifested in the unity of professional-scientific, psychological and socio-communicative components. V.A. Slastenin explains the effectiveness of the pedagogical professional activity by the combination of personal qualities, professional knowledge and pedagogical skills. This approach justifies the systemic nature of the requirements for a teacher of education/In terms of professional-scientific aspects, a future teacher of education should have a deep knowledge of

educational theory, youth psychology, social pedagogy and modern educational technologies.[4] Psychological requirements include such qualities as empathy, emotional stability, pedagogical sensitivity and reflexive thinking. Within the framework of socio-communicative requirements, a culture of communication, social responsibility and readiness for cooperation are manifested as important factors determining the effectiveness of the educational process.

Also, the normative and legal documents in the field of education adopted in the Republic of Uzbekistan recognize the educational activity of a teacher as a social order of society and place high demands on his professional competencies. The Law "On Education" defines the spiritual and moral maturity and professional responsibility of pedagogical personnel as one of the main factors of the quality of education.

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

Today, the professional activity of a future teacher of education is a complex pedagogical and psychological process aimed at ensuring personal development, which requires a high level of professional knowledge, psychological maturity and socio-communicative competencies. The requirements for this activity justify the need to form a teacher as a facilitator who organizes an educational environment, manages communication and supports personal development. In modern educational theory, basic competencies are interpreted as a set of universal qualities that ensure the successful functioning of a person in social, professional and personal life. They are not limited to knowledge within a particular subject, but also include the ability of a person to make independent decisions, communicate, adapt and develop himself in various life situations. In this regard, basic competencies are manifested as an integrative result of the content of education.

Within the framework of our research work, the study of the pedagogical and psychological characteristics of improving the facilitation competencies of future teachers of education requires, first of all, clarification of the content of the concepts of facilitation, competence and competence, and facilitation competence. The educational process, as a complex socio-psychological system aimed at developing the activity, independent thinking and internal potential of the individual, demonstrates the traditional role of the teacher as a transmitter of knowledge as a pedagogical position that supports, directs and is based on cooperation with the learner. In this process, the concept of facilitation means its existence as an important scientific and theoretical category of organizing the educational process.

In scientific sources, facilitation is interpreted as an activity aimed at creating favorable pedagogical and psychological conditions that ensure the self-awareness of a person, the realization of his own capabilities and independent development. In scientific terminology, the concept of "facilitation" (English: facilitate) was initially studied in social psychology as an increase in the effectiveness of a person's activities with the participation of others (social facilitation). However, its introduction into humanistic pedagogy is directly related to the name of K. Rogers, who defined the activation of the internal resources of the learner as the main task of the teacher. K. Rogers interprets facilitation as a process of supporting the natural growth of the individual, rather than hindering his development. According to him, the teacher should not be a controller of the learner, but a subject facilitating the educational process through trust, empathy and open communication. It should be noted that the idea of facilitation was not immediately recognized in the fields of pedagogy, psychology and management. Carl Rogers, in his work "Freedom to Learn" ("Свобода учиться"), notes that the concept of "facilitator of learning" ("фасилитатор учения") can be perceived as an unrealistic, even fantastic, situation in teaching practice, but through his research he proves the opposite. In his opinion, facilitative education

creates an atmosphere of freedom, creativity and responsibility, since the facilitator shares responsibility for the educational process, planning and management methods of educational activities with learners, parents and representatives of the public.

Scholars from the Commonwealth of Independent States, including E.F. Zeer, I.V. Zhizhina, M.N. Dudina, V.V. Kolpachnikov, R.V. Ovcharova, L.N. Kulikova, have studied the theoretical and practical significance of the concept of facilitation.[7]

In pedagogical theory, the concept of facilitation is inextricably linked with constructivist and person-centered educational ideas. According to this approach, knowledge is not given in a ready-made form, but is formed in the process of active student participation, problem situations, and social interaction. In this process, the teacher is not a source of knowledge, but a facilitator who organizes and directs the learning process. This allows us to interpret facilitation not as a method or technique, but as a pedagogical mindset and professional position. Facilitation is, in a broad sense, a professional activity aimed at facilitating the process of achieving a goal for a group or individual, removing obstacles in communication, and revealing the potential of participants. Pedagogical facilitation is a form of this process adapted to the educational environment, which denies the traditional dictation between the teacher and the student. Based on the competency approach of S. Whitdet and S. Halliford, it can be said that pedagogical facilitation is the skill of awakening the “need to learn” in the student [6].

In particular, in the professional activity of a teacher of education, facilitation is an important pedagogical factor in the formation of the socio-communicative activity, value system and personal position of students. An analysis of the scientific literature shows that pedagogical facilitation is characterized by the following fundamental features:

1. Creating an environment of psychological safety: The facilitator-teacher recognizes the student's right to make mistakes, which eliminates the fear factor that blocks the process of critical thinking.

2. Cognitive stimulation: In the process of pedagogical facilitation, knowledge is not given ready-made, but is “discovered” through problematic questions and projects. In this case, the facilitator is not a source of information, but a moderator of the cognitive process.

3. Emotional support (Empathy): As K. Rogers noted, the success of facilitation depends on the teacher's "authenticity" and acceptance of the student as a person. The presented scientific considerations highlight three fundamental features that reveal the essence of pedagogical facilitation and justify their inextricable link. First of all, creating an environment of psychological safety eliminates fear and internal barriers by recognizing the student's right to make mistakes in the educational process and provides the necessary conditions for independent and critical thinking.

In the scientific research of the representative of management psychology R. Boyatzis, competence is associated with functional efficiency. According to his interpretation, competence is a link between the specific characteristics of a person (abilities, behavioral models) and the specific results of work. The analysis of pedagogical and psychological research shows that the concepts of “competence” and “competence” are interconnected in content, but there are certain differences in their scientific essence, functional function and role in describing educational results. Clarifying this distinction is of great importance in ensuring the methodological accuracy of our dissertation research.

Researchers F. Delamare-Le Deist and J. Winterton argue that the concept of competence is not limited to technical skills, but also represents a holistic combination of cognitive, functional

and social meta-competences. That is, competence is a systemic integrity that determines not only the performance of a person in a specific task, but also a strategy for finding solutions to unexpected problems. S. Whitdet and S. Hollyford analyze competence as “measurable behavioral models of a person”. According to their views, if “competence” is a description of a workplace (or a specific position), then “competence” is the real behavior of a person in this position. Within the framework of the “DeSeCo” (Definition and Selection of Competencies) project promoted by the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the content of the concept of competence is harmonized with the “reflexive approach”.

According to this approach, competence is the ability to mobilize a person’s psychological resources and skills in a specific context to meet complex requirements[7]. According to the holistic professional competence model developed by British scientists G. Cheetham and G. Chivers, this concept is divided into such components as cognitive, functional, personal (ethics and attitudes) and meta-competence (self-education). This confirms that competence is based not only on knowledge, but also on the value system of the individual. Analyzing the concept of competence at the operational level requires identifying the functional relationships between its internal elements.

In particular, according to the “Competency Iceberg Model” put forward by L. Spencer and M. Spencer, competence is divided into two layers: surface and deep layers. According to this model, the knowledge and skills of a specialist constitute the surface (visible) part of the iceberg, which is relatively easy to form and measure. However, the basis of competence is its deep-seated social roles, personal qualities and internal motivations, which determine long-term effectiveness. In J. Westera's research, the relationship between the cognitive and practical components of competence is considered through the prism of "contextuality". According to the author, while knowledge is a passive resource, competence is an "active form" of knowledge in a specific situation. This allows us to express competence through the formula "knowledge + action + attitude".

DISCUSSION AND RESULTS

In today's globalization environment, the education of our country's youth has risen to the level of state policy, and therefore one of our main tasks is to protect the youth, who are the creators of our future, from various foreign ideas, ideologies and aggressions aimed at capturing the hearts and minds of people. As the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev noted, “The education of the younger generation has always been important and relevant.

But in the 21st century in which we live, this issue is truly becoming a matter of life and death. In the conditions of today's modernizing Uzbekistan, the sphere of spirituality and enlightenment, education, like all other spheres, needs innovations. In Europe, South Korea, Japan, China, and Russia, there are hundreds of organizations, foundations, and associations engaged in scientific strategies for youth education. Studying their experience, bringing in modern technologies, and using them for the purpose of educating young people in the spirit of the national idea is one of the important requirements for the modernization of higher education. After all, the effectiveness of all reforms being carried out, our Development Strategy depends on the human factor, its spirituality. Therefore, the issues of the national idea, ideological education, and spirituality and enlightenment remain a priority direction of our state policy.

While nations and countries that are indifferent and indifferent to ideological education will disappear from the face of the earth, the nation that educates its youth in the spirit of a modern national idea will live on. Therefore, in the current complex and dangerous period, when

ideological, ideological, and informational struggles are intensifying in the international arena, it is important to organize spiritual and educational work based on the requirements of the times, to form a conscious attitude of our compatriots to life, to increase their sense of involvement in the events taking place around them, and to wage a consistent fight against aggression that could threaten the independence of our country and our peaceful life.

Experts who are impartially approaching the crisis processes taking place in various spheres of life in Western countries, in particular in cultural life, note with sadness that the Western world is on the verge of destruction. No matter how much the spiritual values of other nations influence our society, our national spiritual qualities such as respect for elders and parents, humility, honesty, faith, hard work, and hospitality remain stable. Because these spiritual qualities are ingrained in our blood. "Mass culture", which contradicts the moral, spiritual values of our people about morality, thought, shame, honesty and purity, and human dignity, has a negative impact on the spirituality of young people. The future of our country, the prospects of a new Uzbekistan, and the success of the reforms being carried out in the field of education largely depend on the scientific potential, level, dedication of pedagogical personnel, and their desire to educate the younger generation and raise and mature them as well-rounded individuals. The educational process in any educational institution is directly organized and conducted by teachers. The spiritual and educational activities carried out in our country are based, first of all, on the spiritual and educational heritage of our people. After all, this heritage is a strong source of national ideology and our spirituality. The ideological education of today's students and future specialists requires the implementation of a new task that has not been set before. That is, if previously students were limited to providing knowledge about the national idea, destructive and creative ideas, now they are required to be taught to apply this knowledge in life.

Studying the theory and practice of the educational system in higher educational institutions, analyzing the modern activities of the system, and comprehensively studying pedagogical and other scientific literature shows that didactics and educational theory are taken into account in organizing the activities of the professional education system of students.

The main requirements for the professional education system of students are reflected in the following principles:

- the principle of expediency - the organizational and structural construction of the system in accordance with certain concepts, main ideas, programs, tasks and goals;
- the principle of integrativity - requires the integration of individual differentiated parts and functions of the system into a single whole and gives integrity to this process;
- the principle of educational education - the active use of the educational potential of students in the content of the subjects being taught in order to develop their personal development, form positive motivation for work on themselves, and direct them to creative and practical activities outside of school;
- the principle of uniformity of requirements for professors and group trainers - implies the mutual coordination of the requirements of all objects of the educational process;
- the principle of adaptability - is implemented by adapting the pedagogical system to external and internal factors and conditions;
- the principle of scientificity - a scientific approach to the substantiation of the conceptual aspects of the functioning and development of educational systems;
- the principle of professional orientation - the assimilation of the spiritual and moral rules of the professional community by future specialists;

● the principle of systematicity, continuity and continuity of the activities of the system of professional education of students requires the comprehensive fulfillment of all tasks and the prevention of imbalance and fragmentation.

The above considerations require solving a number of problems in the modernization of modern ideological education.[7]

. In particular: - creating a broad ideological information environment in the life of society;
- determining the need for young people to acquire knowledge about the national idea and achieving thorough mastery of this knowledge, ensuring their acquisition of practical skills and qualifications;

- modernizing the pedagogical foundations of instilling the national idea in the minds of young people;

- increasing the scope and quality of spiritual and educational events organized in higher educational institutions and ensuring their viability.

After all, ideological disputes and information attacks in the world are putting forward new, modern requirements for the ideological education of the growing younger generation. The need to neutralize the influence of foreign ideologies in higher educational institutions is being emphasized. Spiritual and educational work in higher educational institutions is effective only when it is based on certain principles. The main principles that determine the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work include: national ideological orientation, non-partisanship, unity of education and upbringing, vitality, integrity, unity of consciousness and behavior, practicality, mass participation, encouraging student initiative, encouraging good qualities, combating spiritual vices with "Enlightenment against Ignorance", taking into account the future professional characteristics of students, coherence, etc.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

In conclusion, it should be noted that the ideological education of today's students, future specialists, based on the requirements of the new era of Uzbekistan's development, requires modernization on a scientific pedagogical basis, within the framework of preparing students for independent professional spiritual life. That is, if previously it was limited to providing students with knowledge about the national idea, destructive and creative ideas, modernized ideological education turns ideological awareness, competencies into the daily life skills of young people, norms of behavior. After all, at the current stage, the development from national revival to national advancement requires students not only to know the content of spiritual and moral qualities, but also to have the ability to apply them in their daily practical activities.

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